

The verse.

This model is contained within an individuals soul and is mirrored to the left and right side of the soul with a mirror panel in the middle of that individuals soul that mirrors the set of the verse. This is how the major set and minor sets of the verse functions, and it goes as followed:

1. Absolute final perpetual something seen, the absolute final perpetual something seen 0.
2. Absolute final perpetual nothing hidden, the absolute final perpetual nothing hidden 0.
3. Finally nothing seen winner, the finally seen 0.
4. Nothing seen winner, the perpetually seen 0.
5. Something hidden winner, paired final 0, extra final 0, which make the outcome of another final 0.
6. 1st seen winner, 1 paired 1, extra 1, which makes the outcome of another 1.
7. 2nd hidden winner, 2 paired 2, extra 2, which makes the outcome of another 2.
8. 3rd seen winner, 3 paired 3, extra 3, which makes the outcome of another 3.
9. Inner hidden inner 1, 4 paired 4, extra 4, which makes the outcome of another 4.
10. Inner hidden inner 2, 5 paired 5, extra 5, which makes the outcome of another 5.
11. Inner hidden inner 3, 6 paired 6, extra 6, which makes the outcome of another 6.
12. Inner hidden inner 4, 7 paired 7, extra 7, which makes the outcome of another 7.
13. Inner hidden inner 5, 8 paired 8, extra 8, which makes the outcome of another 8.
14. Inner hidden inner 6, 9 paired 9, extra 9, which makes the outcome of another 9.
15. Inner hidden inner 7, 10 paired 10, extra 10, which makes the outcome of another 10.
16. Inner hidden inner 8, 11 paired 11, extra 11, which makes the outcome of another 11.
17. Inner hidden inner 9, 12 paired 12, extra 12, which makes the outcome of another 12.
18. Inner hidden inner 10, 13 paired 13, extra 13, which makes the outcome of another 13.
19. Inner hidden inner 11, 14 paired 14, extra 14, which makes the outcome of another 14.
20. Inner hidden inner 12, 15 paired 15, extra 15, which makes the outcome of another 15.
21. Inner hidden inner 13, 16 paired 16, extra 16, which makes the outcome of another 16.
22. Inner hidden inner 14, 17 paired 17, extra 17, which makes the outcome of another 17.
23. Inner hidden inner 15, 18 paired 18, extra 18, which makes the outcome of another 18.

24. Inner hidden inner 16, 19 paired 19, extra 19, which makes the outcome of another 19.
25. Inner hidden inner 17, 20 paired 20, extra 20, which makes the outcome of another 20.
26. Inner hidden inner 18, 21 paired 21, extra 21, which makes the outcome of another 21.
27. Inner hidden inner 19, 22 paired 22, extra 22, which makes the outcome of another 22.
28. Inner hidden inner 20, 23 paired 23, extra 23, which makes the outcome of another 23.
29. Inner hidden inner 21, 24 paired 24, extra 24, which makes the outcome of another 24.
30. Inner hidden inner 22, 25 paired 25, extra 25, which makes the outcome of another 25.
31. Inner hidden inner 23, 26 paired 26, extra 26, which makes the outcome of another 26.
32. Inner hidden inner 24, 27 paired 27, extra 27, which makes the outcome of another 27.
33. Inner hidden inner 25, 28 paired 28, extra 28, which makes the outcome of another 28.
34. Inner hidden inner 26, 29 paired 29, extra 29, which makes the outcome of another 29.
35. Inner hidden inner 27, 30 paired 30, extra 30, which makes the outcome of another 30.
36. Inner hidden inner 28, 31 paired 31, extra 31, which makes the outcome of another 31.
37. Inner hidden inner 29, 32 paired 32, extra 32, which makes the outcome of another 32.
38. Inner hidden inner 30, 33 paired 33, extra 33, which makes the outcome of another 33.
39. Inner hidden inner 31, 34 paired 34, extra 34, which makes the outcome of another 34.
40. Inner hidden inner 32, 35 paired 35, extra 35, which makes the outcome of another 35.
41. Inner hidden inner 33, 36 paired 36, extra 36, which makes the outcome of another 36.
42. Inner hidden inner 34, 37 paired 37, extra 37, which makes the outcome of another 37.
43. Inner hidden inner 35, 38 paired 38, extra 38, which makes the outcome of another 38.

44. Inner hidden inner 36, 39 paired 39, extra 39, which makes the outcome of another 39.
45. Inner hidden middle 1, 40 paired 40, extra 40, which makes the outcome of another 40.
46. Inner hidden middle 2, 41 paired 41, extra 41, which makes the outcome of another 41.
47. Inner hidden middle 3, 42 paired 42, extra 42, which makes the outcome of another 42.
48. Inner hidden middle 4, 43 paired 43, extra 43, which makes the outcome of another 43.
49. Inner hidden middle 5, 44 paired 44, extra 44, which makes the outcome of another 44.
50. Inner hidden middle 6, 45 paired 45, extra 45, which makes the outcome of another 45.
51. Inner hidden middle 7, 46 paired 46, extra 46, which makes the outcome of another 46.
52. Inner hidden middle 8, 47 paired 47, extra 47, which makes the outcome of another 47.
53. Inner hidden middle 9, 48 paired 48, extra 48, which makes the outcome of another 48.
54. Inner hidden middle 10, 49 paired 49, extra 49, which makes the outcome of another 49.
55. Inner hidden middle 11, 50 paired 50, extra 50, which makes the outcome of another 50.
56. Inner hidden middle 12, 51 paired 51, extra 51, which makes the outcome of another 51.
57. Inner hidden middle 13, 52 paired 52, extra 52, which makes the outcome of another 52.
58. Inner hidden middle 14, 53 paired 53, extra 53, which makes the outcome of another 53.
59. Inner hidden middle 15, 54 paired 54, extra 54, which makes the outcome of another 54.
60. Inner hidden middle 16, 55 paired 55, extra 55, which makes the outcome of another 55.
61. Inner hidden middle 17, 56 paired 56, extra 56, which makes the outcome of another 56.
62. Inner hidden middle 18, 57 paired 57, extra 57, which makes the outcome of another 57.
63. Inner hidden middle 19, 58 paired 58, extra 58, which makes the outcome of another 58.

64. Inner hidden middle 20, 59 paired 59, extra 59, which makes the outcome of another 59.
65. Inner hidden middle 21, 60 paired 60, extra 60, which makes the outcome of another 60.
66. Inner hidden middle 22, 61 paired 61, extra 61, which makes the outcome of another 61.
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68. Inner hidden middle 24, 63 paired 63, extra 63, which makes the outcome of another 63.
69. Inner hidden middle 25, 64 paired 64, extra 64, which makes the outcome of another 64.
70. Inner hidden middle 26, 65 paired 65, extra 65, which makes the outcome of another 65.
71. Inner hidden middle 27, 66 paired 66, extra 66, which makes the outcome of another 66.
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75. Inner hidden middle 31, 70 paired 70, extra 70, which makes the outcome of another 70.
76. Inner hidden middle 32, 71 paired 71, extra 71, which makes the outcome of another 71.
77. Inner hidden middle 33, 72 paired 72, extra 72, which makes the outcome of another 72.
78. Inner hidden middle 34, 73 paired 73, extra 73, which makes the outcome of another 73.
79. Inner hidden middle 35, 74 paired 74, extra 74, which makes the outcome of another 74.
80. Inner hidden middle 36, 75 paired 75, extra 75, which makes the outcome of another 75.
81. Inner hidden outer 1, 76 paired 76, extra 76, which makes the outcome of another 76.
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83. Inner hidden outer 3, 78 paired 78, extra 78, which makes the outcome of another 78.

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104. Inner hidden outer 24, 99 paired 99, extra 99, which makes the outcome of another 99.
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115. Inner hidden outer 35, 110 paired 110, extra 110, which makes the outcome of another 110.
116. Inner hidden outer 36, 111 paired 111, extra 111, which makes the outcome of another 111.
117. Inner seen inner 1, 112 paired 112, extra 112, which makes the outcome of another 112.
118. Inner seen inner 2, 113 paired 113, extra 113, which makes the outcome of another 113.
119. Inner seen inner 3, 114 paired 114, extra 114, which makes the outcome of another 114.
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121. Inner seen inner 5, 116 paired 116, extra 116, which makes the outcome of another 116.
122. Inner seen inner 6, 117 paired 117, extra 117, which makes the outcome of another 117.
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124. Inner seen inner 8, 119 paired 119, extra 119, which makes the outcome of another 119.
125. Inner seen inner 9, 120 paired 120, extra 120, which makes the outcome of another 120.
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224. Middle hidden inner 1, 219 paired 219, extra 219, which makes the outcome of another 219.
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548. Outer seen inner 1, 543 paired 543, extra 543, which makes the outcome of another 543.
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582. Outer seen inner 35, 577 paired 577, extra 577, which makes the outcome of another 577.
583. Outer seen inner 36, 578 paired 578, extra 578, which makes the outcome of another 578.

584. Outer seen middle 1, 579 paired 579, extra 579, which makes the outcome of another 579.
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604. Outer seen middle 21, 599 paired 599, extra 599, which makes the outcome of another 599.
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618. Outer seen middle 35, 613 paired 613, extra 613, which makes the outcome of another 613.
619. Outer seen middle 36, 614 paired 614, extra 614, which makes the outcome of another 614.
620. Outer seen outer 1, 615 paired 615, extra 615, which makes the outcome of another 615.
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622. Outer seen outer 3, 617 paired 617, extra 617, which makes the outcome of another 617.
623. Outer seen outer 4, 618 paired 618, extra 618, which makes the outcome of another 618.

624. Outer seen outer 5, 619 paired 619, extra 619, which makes the outcome of another 619.
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628. Outer seen outer 9, 623 paired 623, extra 623, which makes the outcome of another 623.
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634. Outer seen outer 15, 629 paired 629, extra 629, which makes the outcome of another 629.
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638. Outer seen outer 19, 633 paired 633, extra 633, which makes the outcome of another 633.
639. Outer seen outer 20, 634 paired 634, extra 634, which makes the outcome of another 634.
640. Outer seen outer 21, 635 paired 635, extra 635, which makes the outcome of another 635.
641. Outer seen outer 22, 636 paired 636, extra 636, which makes the outcome of another 636.
642. Outer seen outer 23, 637 paired 637, extra 637, which makes the outcome of another 637.
643. Outer seen outer 24, 638 paired 638, extra 638, which makes the outcome of another 638.

- 644. Outer seen outer 25, 639 paired 639, extra 639, which makes the outcome of another 639.
- 645. Outer seen outer 26, 640 paired 640, extra 640, which makes the outcome of another 640.
- 646. Outer seen outer 27, 641 paired 641, extra 641, which makes the outcome of another 641.
- 647. Outer seen outer 28, 642 paired 642, extra 642, which makes the outcome of another 642.
- 648. Outer seen outer 29, 643 paired 643, extra 643, which makes the outcome of another 643.
- 649. Outer seen outer 30, 644 paired 644, extra 644, which makes the outcome of another 644.
- 650. Outer seen outer 31, 645 paired 645, extra 645, which makes the outcome of another 645.
- 651. Outer seen outer 32, 646 paired 646, extra 646, which makes the outcome of another 646.
- 652. Outer seen outer 33, 647 paired 647, extra 647, which makes the outcome of another 647.
- 653. Outer seen outer 34, 648 paired 648, extra 648, which makes the outcome of another 648.
- 654. Outer seen outer 35, 649 paired 649, extra 649, which makes the outcome of another 649.
- 655. Outer seen outer 36, 650 paired 650, extra 650, which makes the outcome of another 650.
- 656. Last final hidden, last paired last, extra last, which makes the outcome of another last.
- 657. Something seen winner, paired final 0, extra final 0, which makes the outcome of another final 0.
- 658. Nothing hidden winner, the perpetually hidden 0.
- 659. Finally nothing hidden winner, the finally hidden 0.

The list shown above is how the complete major set and complete minor sets of the verse are put together. Within the verse set, there are layers to it. To the major set of the verse, there contains individual pieces to that particular set place, such as the 1st seen winner models, where at first, which is absolute shown above in that list, there are the date mirror models. For each date mirror model stems into 4 year space models. For a year space model, it stems into 4 month timespace models. And for a month timespace model, it stems into 4 day time models. For each individual model of the major set of the verse, stems into a minor set with the associated date mirror models that stem into year space models of that particular minor set, and where those year space models stem into month timespace models of that particular minor set, and where those month

timespace models stem into day time models of that particular minor set. There are also associated twin paradoxes with the models of the verse, where the twin paradox explained goes as followed:

- If the paired models, then the extra model, however, if the extra model, then the outcome model, however, if the outcome model, then the paired models.

There is 4 pieces to a twin paradox, where each part of the major set and minor sets of the verse is grouped into 4 pieces, the paired models, the extra model, and the outcome model, where once the 4 pieces of the twin paradox are put together, that twin paradox is then named. For day time models of a particular level of the major set or minor sets, there exists an inner twin paradox, a middle twin paradox, an outer twin paradox, and a last final hidden twin paradox, where 4 models make the inner twin paradox, where that inner twin paradox stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes, then that middle twin paradox stems into an outer twin paradox comprised of 3 other middle twin paradoxes, and then that outer twin paradox stems into a last final hidden twin paradox comprised of 3 other outer twin paradoxes. Then for month timespace, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 models, and where then that inner twin paradox stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes, and then that middle twin paradox stems into an outer twin paradox comprised of 3 other middle twin paradoxes. Then for year space, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 models, and then from that stems into a middle twin paradox comprised of 3 other inner twin paradoxes. Then for date mirror, there is the inner twin paradox comprised of 4 mirror models. Then the last final hidden day time twin paradox, the outer month timespace twin paradox, the middle year space twin paradox, and the inner date mirror twin paradox are put together, and goes as followed:

- If paired inner date mirror twin paradox with middle year space twin paradox, then outer month timespace twin paradox, however, if outer month timespace twin paradox, then last final hidden day time twin paradox, however, if last final hidden day time twin paradox, then paired inner date mirror twin paradox with middle year space twin paradox.

In the paradox explained and shown above, the inner date mirror twin paradox is paired with the middle year space twin paradox, the extra is the outer month timespace twin paradox, and the outcome is the last final hidden day time twin paradox, where the name of this twin paradox is the century twin paradox.

With the major set and minor sets of the verse, there is an absolute paradox between the finally nothing seen winner 0, and the finally nothing hidden winner 0, where it goes as followed:

- If it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, it is therefore the finally nothing hidden winner 0, however if it is the finally nothing hidden winner 0, therefore it is the

finally nothing seen winner 0. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the finally nothing hidden winner 0. However if it is the finally nothing hidden winner 0, therefore it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, however if it is the finally nothing seen winner 0, it is therefore the finally nothing hidden winner 0. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the finally nothing seen winner 0. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the finally nothing seen winner 0 or the finally nothing hidden winner 0.

The outcome of the absolute paradox shown above produces another layer to the major set of the verse and is where the minor sets of the verse start from, that are connected to individual models of the major set, where the result of that absolute paradox is that it creates the nothing winner absolutely finally perpetually 0.

Set.